

OPINION OF THE CUSTOMERS TOWARDS THE TIME TAKEN ON THE PUBLIC, PRIVATE BANKS ON PROVIDING SELECTIVE SERVICES

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Introduction:

Digital banking has been the mantra for the present generation who use the financial transaction in a prominent way. The reason behind the usage of digital banking can be let known by many ways, but the important reason is time. The digital banking has given the feeling of safety and security. Each bank are becoming more competitive in providing services and framing strategies to retain their customers and increase profitability.

Need for the Study: It is easy to say that digital banking takes few minutes to carry and complete the transactions. The usage of banking is manifold by various ways viz., demand for cash, encashing demand draft, deposit cash, getting cheque book, opening accounts and so on. This study is carried over to find the time taken for using the various services in public and private banks.

Objective of the Study: To analyze the time taken by public sector and private sector banks for providing services to customers.

Area of Study: The study is carried in Tirupur city.

Research Design & Sampling: The Researcher is basically descriptive in nature. The sample respondents were taken based on convenience.

Table 1: Time taken to respond

S.No	Services	Public Ltd Banks				Private Ltd Banks			
		Less Than 10	10 To 30	More Than 30	More Than 1 Hr	Less Than 10	10 To 30	More Than 30	More Than 1 Hr
1	Demand for cash	-	131 (24.5)	159 (29.7)	245 (45.8)	-	20 (3.7)	118 (22.1)	397 (74.2)
2	Encash cash draft	45 (8.4)	96 (17.9)	322 (60.2)	72 (13.5)	76 (14.6)	26 (4.9)	305 (57.0)	128 (23.9)
3	To deposit cash	59 (11.0)	81 (15.1)	126 (23.6)	269 (50.3)	9 (1.7)	104 (19.4)	242 (45.2)	180 (33.6)
4	To purchase a bank draft	81 (15.1)	79 (14.8)	227 (29.9)	148 (27.7)	21 (3.9)	121 (22.6)	255 (47.7)	138 (25.8)
5	To open fixed deposit account	31 (5.8)	81 (15.1)	160 (29.9)	263 (49.2)	10 (1.9)	197 (36.8)	181 (33.8)	147 (27.5)
6	To create local cheque credit to customer accounts	44 (8.2)	99 (18.5)	207 (38.7)	138 (34.6)	80 (15.0)	77 (14.4)	185 (34.6)	193 (36.1)
7	To credit outstation cheques credit to customers accounts	86 (16.1)	165 (30.8)	250 (46.7)	34 (6.4)	89 (16.6)	235 (43.9)	131 (24.5)	80 (15.0)

Source: Primary data

For encashing drafts, a highest 60.2 percent of the public sector customers have stated that it takes more than 30 minutes, and a 57 percent of them have stated that it takes more than 30 minutes. A highest of 50.3 percent of the public sector customers have opined that it takes more than 1 hour and takes more than 30 minutes for depositing cash. For getting a cheque book a highest of 30.6 percent of the customers have stated that it takes more than 1 hour and a highest of 43.4 percent of the private banks customers have opined that it takes more than 30 minutes. For purchasing a draft a highest of 42.4 percent of public sector customers and 47.7 percent of private sector customers have stated that it takes more than 30 minutes. In case for opening a fixed deposit account a highest of 49.2 percent of public sector banks customers and a 33.8 percent of the private sector bank customers have opined that it takes more than 1 hour and takes more than 30 minutes respectively.

Table 2: Chi square results (Public sector Banks)

H0: There is no significant association between the Demographic Profile and the time taken on using varied service provided by the Public Sector Bank.

H1: There is a significant association between the Demographic profile and the time taken on using varied service provided by the Public Sector Bank

S.No	Service	Gender		Age Group		Marital Status	
		Chi. Value	Result	Chi. Value	Result	Chi. Value	Result
1	Demand for Cash	0.917	NS	0.008	S	0.005	S
2	Encash cash Draft	0.431	NS	0.704	NS	0.739	NS
3	To Deposite cash	0.147	NS	0.773	NS	0.949	NS
4	To get new Cheque	0.21	NS	0.356	NS	0.04	S
5	To purchase bank draft	0.969	NS	0.2	NS	0.173	NS
6	To open fixed account	0.57	NS	0.296	NS	0.188	NS

Education Qualification		Occupation		Gross Annual Income		Sector Employed	
Chi. Value	Result	Chi. Value	Result	Chi. Value	Result	Chi. Value	Result
0.414	NS	0.929	NS	0.293	NS	0.59	NS
0.294	NS	0.789	NS	0.602	NS	0.912	NS
0.55	NS	0.583	NS	0.652	NS	0.675	NS
0.539	NS	0.459	NS	0.734	NS	0.181	NS
0.426	NS	0.911	NS	0.442	NS	0.623	NS
0.452	NS	0.619	NS	0.444	NS	0.803	NS

S- Significant, NS- Not Significant

* Significant at 5 percent level of significance

Conclusion:

From the study it was understood that the demographic profile of the customer and the time taken for various services of public sector bank it shows non significance in case of the gender, age group, educational qualification, occupation, gross annual incomes and sector employed and shows significance in case of marital status.

Table 3: Chi square results (Private Sector Banks)

H0: There is no significant association between the Demographic Profile and the time taken on using varied service provided by the Private Sector Bank.

H1: There is a significant association between the Demographic profile and the time taken on using varied service provided by the Private Sector Bank

S.No	Service	Gender		Age Group		Marital Status	
		Chi. Value	Result	Chi. Value	Result	Chi. Value	Result
1	Demand for Cash	0.074	NS	0.99	NS	0.351	NS
2	Encash cash Draft	0.915	NS	0.131	NS	0.021	S
3	To Deposit cash	0.416	NS	0.582	NS	0.557	NS
4	To get new Cheque	0.268	NS	0.835	NS	0.181	S
5	To purchase bank draft	0.876	NS	0.539	NS	0.17	NS
6	To open fixed account	0.04	S	0.832	NS	0.132	NS

Education Qualification		Occupation		Gross Annual Income		Sector Employed	
Chi. Value	Result	Chi. Value	Result	Chi. Value	Result	Chi. Value	Result
0.267	NS	0.213	NS	0.845	NS	0.195	NS
0.095	NS	0.877	NS	0.684	NS	0.706	NS
0.517	NS	0.222	NS	0.937	NS	0.238	NS
0.443	NS	0.975	NS	0.819	NS	0.574	NS
0.188	NS	0.605	NS	0.251	NS	0.245	NS
0.604	NS	0.541	NS	0.923	NS	0.469	NS

S- Significant, NS- Not Significant

* Significant at 5 percent level of significance

Conclusion:

From the study it was understood that the demographic profile of the customer and the time taken for various services of public sector bank it shows non significance in case of the gender, age group, educational qualification, occupation, gross annual incomes and sector employed and shows significance in case of marital status

References:

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